

Social Status of Kumbhari Village in Jath Tehsil

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Abstract:

Status is the relative degree to which members of a society hold more or less social value, in other words, based on widely shared beliefs about who they regard as superior in terms of competence or moral qualities. Status is determined by the possession of various characteristics culturally considered to indicate superiority or inferiority (eg. confident manner of speech or race). As such, people use status hierarchies to allocate resources, leadership positions, and other forms of power. In doing so, these shared cultural beliefs make the unequal distribution of resources and power seem natural and just, a support system of social stratification. Sociologist Max Weber explained three central aspects of stratification in society: class, status, and power. In his scheme, which is still influential today, people attain status in the sense of honour because they belong to specific groups with unique lifestyles and privileges. Modern sociologists and social psychologists have expanded this understanding of status to refer to one's relative level of respect and dignity. A social survey examines some demographic factors that may be important in showing the social conditions of study area. Caste system is seen to have a very important place in the Indian family system. Caste system is a long tradition in India. Same like cast system all parameters of living standard in the social manner are examined in this research article.

Keywords: Status, Social Status etc.

Introduction:

Social status is an aggregate measure of an individual's or family's social position in relation to others, an individual's work experience and economic and sociological integration. While analysing the socio-economic status of the family, the income of the family, education and occupation of the earners as well as the combined income of the family members are examined. Socio-economic status is generally broken down into three levels (high, middle and low). To describe it one has to look at the stratum into which a family or an individual falls. Any or all three variables (income, education, and occupation) may be assessed when placing a family or individual into one of these categories.

In upper caste families education is generally more important within the family as well as within the local community. In poor areas, where food, shelter and safety are priorities, education cannot be given special importance. India is predominantly a rural country with two-thirds of its population. The share of rural economy in national income is 46 percent. Even with increasing urbanization, more than half of India's population is projected to be rural by 2050. Agriculture is an important sector of the Indian economy. Because it contributes about 17% to the total GDP. It also provides employment to more than 60% of the population. Indian agriculture sector has registered remarkable growth in the last few decades.

Study Area:

Kumbhari village is in Jat taluka of Sangli district. The total area of this village is 2118.75 hectares. The east-west distance of this village is 5.2 km and the north-south distance is 5.4 km. To the east of this village is the main state highway. It also has Vashan village on the north, Rampur on the east, Daflapur on the west, Mirwat on the south. Kumbhari village is divided into 15 Wards. There is a famous Lakhbai Devi temple in Kumbhari village. This temple is adjacent to the village in the west. A big yatra is held here every year. Thousands of devotees come in large numbers for this yatra.

Objectives:

1. To study the Social Status of the Kumbhari Village.

Research Methodology:

The Primary and Secondary data are used for this present research. The data has been collected from many sources, like

Primary data: Researcher had randomly visited to the villagers and collected information through questionnaire and schedules.

Secondary data: Secondary data collected from the socio-economics abstracts of Sangli Districts, Books, magazines, Research paper etc.

The collected information is finally classified and by applying various cartographic techniques presented in the form of table, graphs and maps.

Social Status:**1) Family System:**

A socio-economic survey examines some demographic factors that may be important in showing the social conditions of your subject. Caste system is seen to have a very important place in the Indian family system. Caste system is a long tradition in India. According to the caste

system in Kumbhari village, the family system is classified as follows

Caste wise family system:

Cast	Families	Percent
OPEN	4	3
OBC	50	39
SC	32	25
NT	43	33

Fig. 2: Caste-Wise Distribution of Families

The survey conducted by us showed that the Other Backward (OBC) community has the largest number of households and population in Kumbhari village. Other Backward (OBC) communities constitute 39 percent of the population of the village. Among these, the population of Nomadic (NT) community is 33 percent, Scheduled Caste (SC) population is 25 percent and the lowest is open category. Maratha comes in open category. The population of Maratha community is found to be 03 percent.

2) Size of Family:

Classes	No. of Families
Below 2	17
3 to 5	60
6 to 9	43
above 9	8

Fig. 3: Size of Family

To study the family system in Kumbhari village groups have been divided based on the number of family members. About 60% of these families have 3 to 5 members in one family. Below that, the number of families with 6 to 9 members is 43%, the number of 2 and less than 2 members is up to 17%. Also, the number of members having more than 9 is about 8 percent. From this it can be seen that joint family system is more common in Kumbhari village.

3) Housing Status:

From the survey in Kumbhari village we observed that most of the family houses were of concrete type. From this it can be seen that the social condition of the people of this village must be good. The percentage of fixed houses in Kumbhari village is almost 69 percent. Along with this, the number of raw houses is seen to be 28%. It is observed during the survey that the number of temporary houses is the lowest which is around 01%.

House Type	No. of Houses	Percent
Kaccha	38	30
Pakka	86	69
Temporary	1	1

Fig. 4: House Condition

4) Drinking Water Facility :

Sources	Sources
Hand pump	61
Tank	26
Tap	16
Well	19

Through the survey we can see that hand pump is the most used for drinking water in Kumbhari village. At the same time, the lowest consumption is seen from wells.

Fig. 5 Sources of Drinking Water

Kumbhari Gram Panchayat has provided drinking water to households but we find that some people are deprived of this water. We find that the number of families who get drinking water through taps is also less.

3.2.5 Availability of drinking water:

Classes	No. of Families
Within Premises (<10m)	76
Near Premises (10-50m)	21
Away (>50m)	26

Fig. 6: Location of Drinking Water

We studied the availability of water in Kumbhari village through survey in three different ways. Among them, the number of households having access to drinking water from a distance of less than 10 meters is the highest. That is, drinking water is found to be available to almost half of the houses in the village through taps by the Gram Panchayat. But since most of the population of Kumbhari village lives in different settlements, it is not possible for the Gram Panchayat to arrange tap water. It was found that the number of households that had to travel at least 50 meters to fetch drinking water was the lowest. The drinking water system of a family living in a mansion is seen to be distributed through a pipe.

6) Latrine Facility :

Table No. 6: Attached Latrine Facilities	
Type	No. of Families
Attached	57
Common	10
No Facility	33

Fig.7: Latrine Facilities

In Kumbhari village, the concept of hagandari free village is not seen to be implemented. The highest number of households having their own toilet is 57 percent. 10% occur in households using public toilets. Almost 33% households still do not have access to toilet facilities. These families are still seen going to the toilet in the open. In Kumbhari Gram Panchayat, the use of toilets is less.

7) Sewage System :

Table No. 7: Drainage Facility		
Type	No. of Families	Percentage
Piped/Closed	20	17
Open Pit	35	30
No Drainage	61	53

Fig. 8: Drainage Facility

During this survey we have taken information about the sewage system in Kumbhari Gram Panchayat. 17% of households were found to have sewer system to discharge sewage. It is seen that 30% of the households have arranged septic tank to discharge the waste water. Still there are families under Gram Panchayat who do not have any sewage facility. There are about 53% of households that still discharge sewage in the open.

8) Source of Electricity :

Table No. 8: Sources of Light		
Type	No. of Families	Percentage
Solar/Electricity	120	88
Kerosine/wood	3	2
No Light	14	10

Fig. 9: Sources of Light

When electricity consumption is studied in Kumbhari village, it is found that 88 percent of households use electricity. Also, kerosene and wood are still used as fuel in 2 percent of the houses. So in 10 percent of the houses today this system of light is not found.

9) Household Appliances :

Type	No. of Families	Percentage
TV	63	53
Refrigerator	28	23
No Facility	28	24

Fig. 10: Home Appliances

When studying the use of household appliances in Kumbhari village, it is found that 53 percent of the households have TVs. This device is used. Also, refrigerator is used in 10 percent of homes. So in 24 percent homes, no device is used yet.

10) Use of Vehicles :

Type	No. of Families
Tractor	35
2 Wheeler	69
4 Wheeler	14
Other	4

Fig. 11: Use of Vehicles

When the vehicle usage in Kumbhari village is studied, it is found that 69 percent of the families use two wheelers. Also, tractors are used at 35 percent, four wheelers are used at 14 percent and some families have other vehicles and its percentage is 4 percent.

Conclusion:

Kumbhari village is divided into 15 *wadi*. Therefore, the social development of this village is not found. Agriculture is the main occupation of the people of Kumbhari village. Also, most of the youths of the village are in the Indian Guards Army. The village Kumbhari has primary and secondary education facilities. The Other Backward (OBC) community has the largest number of houses and population in Kumbhari village. Other Backward (OBC) communities constitute 39 percent of the population of the village. Among these, Nomadic (NT) community is 33 percent, Scheduled Caste (SC) population is 25 percent and the lowest is open category. Maratha comes in open category. The population of Maratha community is found to be 03 percent. According to the study of family system in Kumbhari village, the number of 3 to 5 members in a family is about 60%. From this it can be seen that joint family system is more common in Kumbhari village. The percentage of fixed houses in Kumbhari village is almost 69 percent.

In Kumbhari village, hand pump is the most used for drinking water and well is the least used. The number of houses having access to drinking water from a distance of less than 10

meters is the highest when water availability in Kumbhari village is first. In Kumbhari village, the concept of hagandari free village is not seen to be implemented. Almost 33% households still do not have access to toilet facilities. The extent of sewage system in Kumbhari Gram Panchayat is low. There are almost 53% of households that still discharge sewage in the open. 53 percent of the household appliances in Kumbhari village is TV. This device is used.

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